

Separation of respiration and perfusion in Electrical Impedance Tomography by harmonic analysis

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Abstract: In this contribution we illustrate a post-acquisition method for the separation of perfusion and respiration components in Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT). In this method a harmonic analysis of the EIT transient is performed taking advantage of the fact that the perfusion and the respiration can easily be distinguished by their relative frequency. In fact, EIT transients can be reconstructed as a summation of amplitude modulated signals some of which belonging to the respiration and some others to the perfusion. Here we show preliminary results on EIT reconstructed snapshots where respiration and perfusion information are completely decoupled.

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I. Introduction

Electrical impedance tomography (EIT) is an electrical measurement routinely performed in the medical field to follow the respiration of a patient. However, EIT measurements do not contain only information about respiration, but also about cardiac dynamics and perfusion.

Nevertheless, given the large difference in their relative amplitudes and the superposition of their frequency bands, the separation of respiration and perfusion signals is a challenging task. Several approaches were proposed such as principal component analysis with a frequency domain filtering [1] and Gaussian process regression [2].

In this contribution the separation of perfusion and ventilation signals is undertaken in a post-acquisition elaboration through harmonic analysis, that is analyzing the trend of the EIT signals in the frequency domain.

This method is based on several assumptions: (i) respiration and perfusion can be expressed as a sum of amplitude modulated signals, (ii) the frequencies of respiration and perfusion are stable in the time window of the analysis, (iii) the envelopes of the modulation are smooth enough to be expressed as a low order polynomial, (iv) respiration and perfusion do not share any harmonic, and (v) perfusion and cardiac changes exhibit the same frequency.

Given a series of EIT images, harmonic analysis was performed on the first principal components (Principal Component Analysis PCA scores) to decouple respiration and perfusion and subsequently a series of snapshots containing only perfusion- or respiration- related

information were reconstructed. This strategy could easily be automatized for the localization of the heart in the EIT images.

II. Material and methods

The dataset for the analysis came from a deeply sedated, intubated, and ventilated patient on who a positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) step maneuver was performed at Szeged University Hospital, Hungary. The EIT data were collected at the 5th inter-costal space (ICS 5) at 50 Hz with a PulmoVista500 (Draeger Medical, Germany) and the EIT images were produced through a Newton-Rapson reconstruction algorithm.

The procedure to produce frequency related snapshots was composed of five steps. First, (i) split the dataset into suitable parts, in this case different PEEP steps. Then (ii) perform a principal component analysis (PCA) of the selected image frames to reduce the amount of data to process. (iii) Find the frequencies of interest (see [3] for details). (iv) Apply harmonic analysis (least square minimization) on the first principal components (PCA scores) and finally (v) reconstruct the frequency-selected snapshots using the PCA loading matrix.

At this point a snapshot for every frequency, which contains pixel-wise information about amplitude, phase, and temporal trend (modulation) of that frequency can be created.

The least square minimization was performed in the frequency domain following Hallems et al. procedure

[4]. In fact, from Assumptions (i) to (v) an EIT temporal trend $\Delta Z(t)$ can be expressed as:

$$\Delta Z(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{N_f} A_j(t) \cos(2\pi f_j t) - B_j(t) \sin(2\pi f_j t) \quad (1)$$

where f_j are the particular frequencies composing the signals, which are either the harmonics of the respiration or of the cardiac changes, and $A_j(t)$ and $B_j(t)$ are smooth polynomials whose coefficients were recovered by least-squares parameter identification. These coefficients contain information about amplitude and phase of every signal.

III. Results and discussion

Some results of the method are reported in Fig 1 which shows a snapshot for the cardiac dynamics/perfusion signal (a) and a snapshot for the respiration one (b).

Figure 1: Frequency-selected snapshot. a) Absolute value of the perfusion signal. b) Phase of the respiration signal.

The first snapshot was created selecting the frequency of the perfusion (*approx.* 1.5 Hz) and then elaborating the pixel-wise information to obtain the amplitude of the perfusion or of the cardiac signal. The second snapshot, instead, was recovered from the respiration frequency (*approx.* 0.25 Hz) and displays the *phase* of the respiration.

Every pixel in the snapshots are the averaged amplitude of the perfusion (Fig 1 a) and the averaged phase of the respiration at the pixel position (Fig 1 b).

In Fig 1 a) most of the intensity was concentrated in a circular region in the left ventral area which may be the expected position of the heart. However, some intensity was also localized in the bottom half of the snapshot which corresponded to the dorsal part area.

On the other hand, in Fig 1 b) the central patch at low relative phase may be assigned to the lung area. This patch showed a difference of phase of *approx.* 180° against the surrounding, meaning that while the conductivity of the central path was growing in time the conductivity of the surrounding was decreased at a similar rate. This illustrates how a phase-related snapshot can produce large contrast between regions with opposite temporal behavior.

IV. Conclusions

In this contribution we introduced a novel method for a post-acquisition separation of perfusion and respiration signals in EIT images. This approach was based on the harmonic analysis of EIT transients which can be decomposed into a combination of amplitude modulated signals. With this approach it is possible to reconstruct EIT snapshots which contained only some respiratory or some cardiac related pieces of information.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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